

1 **The timing of antenatal glucocorticoids determines the receptor sensitivity in preterm**
2 **infants**

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7 **Abstract:**

8 *Context:* The global preterm birth rate is about 11%, most of premature (PI) infants receive
9 antenatal glucocorticoids (aGC) to accelerate fetal lung maturation, however, this treatment
10 increases the vulnerability for immune disorders later in life.

11 *Objective.* We hypothesized that aGC given at the “wrong” time of day, determines the
12 vulnerability. We compared the effect of aGCs in PI exposed in the morning (in-phase, IP with
13 the maternal circadian rhythms) and in the evening (out-of-phase, OP) to controls (C).

14 *Design and setting.* We collected data and blood samples from infants enrolled in a
15 population-based cohort study. Groups are balanced in gestational age, birth weight and
16 sex. Infants were divided depending on the time of maternal cortisol peak. Exclusion criteria
17 was established by the cohort, additionally infants born before gestational week 24 and
18 exposed to postnatal GCs were excluded.

19 *Patients.* The study was run in sub-cohorts, GC receptor (GR) sensitivity was assessed on 6
20 IP and 6OP. RNA sequencing, RNA expression and DNA methylation was assessed in

1 peripheral blood cells from 13 C, 17 IP and 17 OP. All samples were obtained on average 10
2 days after birth.

3 *Interventions.* No interventions were performed.

4 *Results.* OP infants exhibited reduced GR sensitivity and suppressed expression of genes
5 involved in antibody production, leucocyte migration, antigen presentation.

6 *Conclusions.* aGCs exposure aligned with the maternal GC rhythms, would be advisable to
7 improve PI's capacity to fight against pathogens in the first weeks of life.

8

9

10

11 **Introduction:**

12 Approximately 15 million babies are born too early each year, corresponding to a global
13 preterm birth rate of about 11%¹. While the survival and neurological prognosis improve with
14 advancing gestational age and birth weight, outcomes strongly depend on the early
15 environment/treatments they are exposed to^{2,3}. The antenatal glucocorticoid (aGC) therapy
16 is indicated to more than 90% of mothers at risk of preterm delivery between 24 and 34
17 weeks of gestation. Synthetic GCs (GC) accelerate fetal lung maturation and reduce the risk
18 of respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), the leading cause of mortality in preterm infants⁴.
19 While being beneficial for infants' survival, aGC treatment has been associated with an
20 increased vulnerability to develop neurobehavioral and immune disorders later in life,

1 effects attributed to permanent changes in the stress axis activity and in the homeostasis of
2 endogenous GCs⁵⁻¹⁰.

3 GCs are steroid hormones with widespread physiologic actions, modulating stress,
4 metabolic and immune responses upon activation of nuclear receptors that mainly act as
5 transcription factors (reviewed in¹¹). GCs receptor (GR) is expressed in a wide variety of cells,
6 evoking cell-type specific transcriptional responses in magnitude and directionality¹¹. GCs
7 are produced by the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal (HPA axis) with a circadian pattern,
8 peaking before the active phase (i.e.: morning in humans)¹². During pregnancy, only 10% of
9 the maternal GCs cross placenta driving essential growth and tissue maturation¹³ while also
10 providing circadian timing cues to the fetus^{14,15}. We have previously shown that the circadian
11 phase of aGC exposure is relevant for the long-term neurodevelopmental outcomes¹⁶. In
12 both, mice and preterm infants, the administration of pharmacological doses of synthetic
13 GCs out-of-phase (i.e., evening in humans and misaligned with the maternal physiological
14 GC rhythms) lead to an impaired regulation of the stress axis (i.e., hyperactivity, anxiety, low
15 stress coping capacity) later in life. However, when the administration was in-phase (aligned
16 with the maternal GC rhythms), the offspring showed a behavioral phenotype comparable
17 to non-exposed individuals. In the mouse model, we found that these long-lasting changes
18 are explained at the molecular level by an altered GCs homeostasis including reduced
19 sensitivity of the GC receptor (GR)¹⁶.

20 In the present study, we assessed the effect of the antenatal administration with GCs in
21 preterm babies considering the time of day of the exposure with special focus on the
22 potential differences in GR sensitivity and its functional consequences. The sensitivity of the

1 glucocorticoid receptor (GR) is regulated by several mechanisms (reviewed by¹⁷⁻²⁰),
2 including the interaction with a multi-protein complex that anchors the GR in its inactive
3 form in the cytosol. This multi-protein complex including chaperones (heat shock protein 90
4 (hsp90), hsp70) and immunophilins (FK506-binding protein 5 (FKBP5) and FKBP4), prevent
5 GR from acting as a transcription factor in the absence of GCs, while maintaining a
6 conformation with high hormone affinity^{21,22}. In presence of GC, the complex GR-GC
7 translocate to the nucleus, binds to GC responsive elements (GREs) and induces/represses
8 gene expression^{23,24}. Interestingly, the expression of *FKBP5* is induced by GR-GC, favoring an
9 intracellular negative feedback loop in which FKBP5 protein inhibits the nuclear
10 translocation of GR, thus, being key in controlling its sensitivity²⁵⁻²⁸.

11 Here we first assessed general transcriptional changes in peripheral blood mononuclear
12 cells (PBMCs) from preterm infants exposed to aGCs and term controls. We found profound
13 transcriptional changes and interestingly, a lower inferred activity of the GR in exposed
14 infants. Therefore, we assessed GR sensitivity in preterm infants focusing now on the time of
15 aGCs exposure. We found that preterm infants exposed to GCs in the late evening (out-of-
16 phase) exhibited reduced GR sensitivity compared to those infants exposed in the morning
17 (in-phase). While the main regulator of GR sensitivity, *FKBP5*, was expressed at a similar level
18 between the groups, we found differential levels of methylation on regulatory regions of the
19 *FKBP5* promoter. These regulatory sequences serve as binding sites of transcriptions factors
20 (TF) upstream of several innate and adaptive immunity pathways. By comparing the
21 transcriptome of PBMCs from babies depending on the time of GC exposure, we found
22 pronounced changes on the expression of genes involved in antibody production and B cell

1 signaling, leucocyte migration and proliferation, antigen presentation and cellular stress
2 responses in those exposed out of phase. Our data suggests that aGC in the morning, in-
3 phase and aligned with the maternal GC rhythms, would be advisable in the clinics to
4 minimize the altered expression of those immune pathways and likely improve the capacity
5 of preterm infants to fight against pathogens during the first weeks of life.

6

7 **Materials and methods:**

8 **Premature babies' cohort:** Data and blood samples for the present study were obtained from a
9 population-based multicenter cohort study. The IRoN (ImmunoRegulation of the Newborn) study is
10 a prospective observational cohort designed to characterize immune regulation and adaptation,
11 microbiome development, and infection-related outcomes in term and preterm infants, with the
12 overarching aim of defining individual risk profiles for adverse neonatal outcomes in relation to multi-
13 level exposures (environmental, medical, infectious, and pharmacological, both antenatal and
14 postnatal). Longitudinal collection of blood samples (among others) and comprehensive analyses
15 of immunoregulatory and molecular factors was prospectively planned, including cellular immune
16 profiling, microbiome sequencing, and additional molecular assays related to perinatal exposures.
17 The study protocol explicitly covered the assessment of immunoregulatory mechanisms, modifiable
18 perinatal exposures, and their association with short- and long-term clinical outcomes. Since
19 around 90% of preterm infants are exposed to aGCs, our study focused on this major
20 pharmacological intervention. While GR sensitivity, DNA methylation, and transcriptomic profiling
21 were not specified as primary endpoints in the original protocol, these analyses were conducted as
22 predefined secondary exploratory investigations to environmental/drug exposure within the
23 approved framework. Accordingly, the readouts reported here constitute secondary exploratory

1 analyses within the approved cohort. The fresh blood samples and isolated PBMCs used for the
2 present analyses exclusively consisted of remnant material from clinically indicated or protocol-
3 defined study samples, no additional blood draws were performed for this project. The blood volume
4 (< 1% of body blood volume per blood sampling) was in line with current guidelines of the European
5 Medical Agency (EMA) on the investigation of medicinal products in term and preterm infants;
6 Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use and Pediatric Committee (PDCO, 2009). The IRoN
7 study was approved by the local ethics committee (approval no. IRoN AZ 2024_222, before
8 AZ15_304). The informed consent signed by parents enrolling the babies in the IRoN study informs
9 about the possibility that biomaterials and data could be passed on, in an anonymous form, to other
10 institutions for research purposes only. For this study, we retrospectively collected data from the
11 IRoN study on gestational age at birth, birth weight, sex and the timing of antenatal synthetic GC
12 (betamethasone, 8 or 12 mg) injections – at least two injections 24 h apart – given to the mother
13 between weeks 24 and 34 of gestation. Depending on the time of maternal physiological cortisol
14 peak (estimated at 0800 h¹²) and the time of antenatal betamethasone injection, infants were divided
15 into two groups: the in-phase group, injected between 0600 h and 1200 h and the out-of-phase
16 group, injected between 1800 h and 0000 h. The infants from the control group were not exposed to
17 aGCs because they were born term. Exclusion criteria were those established by the IRoN cohort
18 and additionally dexamethasone treatment (because doses are given every 12 h), single
19 betamethasone treatments, birth before gestational week 24 and postnatal GCs treatment. This
20 study was run in three sub-cohorts described in Table 1. Briefly, the GR sensitivity assay was
21 performed on n=6 fresh blood samples per group entirely based on the availability. The RNA and DNA
22 samples were obtained from PBMCs. For RNA sequencing, RNA expression and DNA methylation
23 assays, we included: n=13 controls, n=17 in-phase and n=17 out-of-phase infants. The assessment

1 of the immune cell profile was done within the IRoN study including n=28 in-phase and n=48 out-of-
2 phase infants. All samples included in this study were obtained on average 10 days after birth.

3
4 **Glucocorticoid receptor sensitivity:** was assessed by an *ex-vivo* assay in which fresh blood
5 samples were incubated with lipopolysaccharide (LPS, L2630, Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri,
6 USA) to activate the production of the pro-inflammatory cytokine interleukin 6 (IL-6). We
7 used twelve fresh blood samples (remnants of the samples routinely taken for diagnostics
8 depending on the availability) from babies exposed to aGCs either in- or out-of-phase (6/per
9 group, Table 1). Babies were born on average 10 days before this sample was taken always
10 between 0800 h and 1000 h in EDTA-coated tubes. Fifty μ L aliquot was incubated with 100
11 ng/mL of LPS and with LPS and dexamethasone (DEX, D2915, Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri, USA)
12 at different concentrations (0.01, 0.1 and 1 μ M) for 12 h at 37°C. After incubation, samples
13 were centrifuged (10,000 xg for 10 m) and IL-6 production quantified in duplicates by ELISA
14 in the supernatant (EH2IL6, RRID: AB_3731284, ThermoFisher, Massachusetts, USA).

15
16 **PBMCs isolation from blood:** To isolate peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) from
17 whole neonatal blood we used density-gradient centrifugation with Ficoll. Remnants of EDTA
18 blood samples taken between 0800 h and 1000 h, from babies born in average 10 days before
19 were used to isolate PBMCs. Blood samples from n=13 controls, n=17 in-phase and n=17
20 out-of-phase infants were diluted 1:1 with PBS, layered over the density gradient medium,
21 centrifuged at 1000 x g for 20 m at room temperature (RT) with the brake off. PBMCs form a

1 distinct cloudy band at the interface that was carefully removed, transferred in a new tube,
2 washed with PBS and centrifuged at 400 x g for 10 m at RT. The supernatant was discarded,
3 and the cell pellet used for DNA and RNA isolation.

4
5 **DNA and RNA isolation:** Genomic DNA and total RNA were simultaneously extracted from
6 babies' PBMCs frozen samples using the AllPrep DNA/RNA/miRNA Universal Kit (80224,
7 Qiagen, Hilden Germany) following the manufacturer's protocol. Briefly, PBMC samples
8 were thawed on ice and centrifuged for 10 m at 4°C and 20000 x g. The pellet was
9 homogenized in RLT Plus sample buffer, and genomic DNA and RNA were isolated according
10 to manufacturer's instructions. The concentration and purity of samples were measured
11 using Epoch Microplate Spectrophotometer. Total RNA was stored at -80°C and DNA was
12 stored at -20°C.

13
14 **DNA methylation assay:** A total of 500 ng of genomic DNA was converted to bisulfite DNA
15 (bisDNA) utilizing the EpiTect Fast DNA Bisulfite Kit (59802, Qiagen, Hilden Germany)
16 according to manufacturer's instructions and eluted in 50 µL of EB buffer (provided by the
17 kit). Subsequently, 10 ng of bisDNA were amplified at 56°C for 40 cycles with the PyroMark
18 PCR Kit (978801, Qiagen, Hilden Germany) using the respective forward and reverse primers
19 for each CpG-assay (NR3C1 (GR): Fwd bisPCR: TTTTGGGGAGGTTTTAGGG; Rev bisPCR:
20 [biotin]TCTACTTTACAACCTCTCTCCAATA and FKBP5: Fwd bisPCR:
21 GGTTATTGTGAGGATGATAGTAGTT; Rev bisPCR: [biotin]CCCAAACCTATACTACCTACCAA).
22 Quality of amplification was assessed in a 1% agarose gel electrophoresis. Pyrosequencing

1 was performed on the PyroMark Autoprep Q48 (9002471, Qiagen, Hilden Germany) utilizing
2 the Q48 Advanced CpG Reagents according to manufacturer instructions and the
3 perspective sequencing primer (NR3C1 Pyrosequencing primers: GGGAGGTTTTAGGGAA;
4 FKBP5 Pyrosequencing: TTGGGGGTGGGGATT). Sequencing results that did not pass quality
5 control were discarded (NR3C1 (GR): 3 controls, 1 in-phase and 1 out-of-phase; FKBP5: 4
6 from each group). Thus, we then obtained data from n=10 controls, n=16 in-phase and n=16
7 out-of-phase infant samples in the NR3C1 (GR) methylation assay. In the case of FKBP5, we
8 obtained methylation assay data for n=9 controls, n=13 in-phase and n=13 out-of-phase
9 infant samples.

10
11 **RNA sequencing and data analysis:** Total RNA samples were sent to Novogene (Germany),
12 where mRNA quality was checked to confirm suitability for sequencing. RNA libraries were
13 then prepared via poly(A) selection and reverse transcription into cDNA, followed by library
14 quality assessment. Sequencing was performed using 150 bp paired-end reads on an
15 Illumina PE150 platform in n=13 controls, n=17 in-phase and n=17 out-of-phase infant
16 samples. Quality of sequencing was assessed with fastqc (v0.12.0) and fastq files were
17 mapped to the GRCh38 human reference genome with HISAT2²⁹. Subsequently, gene
18 expression matrix (features x samples) was filtered for not-expressed genes by excluding all
19 genes that are not detected in 5% of all samples (counts = 0 in > 2 samples) followed by an
20 additional filtering for low-expressed genes excluding all genes that display less than an
21 average of 10 counts to confirm reliable and robust quantification. A total of 13866 genes are
22 ubiquitously expressed across all samples. Differential expression analysis was performed

1 in DESeq2 (v1.46.0). For pair-wise comparison between aGCs exposed and control (C)
2 infants, DEG analysis was adjusted for covariates of birth weight and gestational age, since
3 groups displayed significant differences for both confounding factors (Fig S1a and b³⁰). This
4 was achieved by including both parameters in the generalized linear model design (GLM) of
5 DESeq2 as covariates (design =~ gestational age + birthweight + aGCs). Birth weight values
6 were missing for one control child (C14), and gestational age values were missing for one
7 control child (C14) and three out-of-phase children (OP5, OP6, OP12). Missing values were
8 mathematically imputed with the mean of each corresponding group as described
9 previously³¹. Genes were considered differentially expressed with an $\text{abs}(\log_2\text{FC}) > 1$ and p-
10 value < 0.05 . Subsequently, raw counts were variance stabilized utilizing variance-stabilizing
11 transformation (VSD) for principal component analysis. For gene set enrichment analysis
12 (GSEA) to identify gene ontology (GO) terms and transcription factor activity analysis, genes
13 were ranked descending based on $\log_2\text{FoldChange} * -\log_{10}(\text{p-value})$ and GSEA for GO terms
14 was performed with clusterProfiler (v4.14.6). GSEA results were adjusted for multiple testing
15 utilizing FDR (0.05). The top active and suppressed GO pathways based on the normalized
16 enrichment score (NES) from each pair-wise comparison were displayed in dot plots. For
17 collapsing related enriched GO-terms within a superior parental term, rrvgo (v1.18.0) was
18 utilized. In brief, a semantic similarity measure was performed, including relative
19 information content. GO terms with a similarity > 0.7 were grouped together to a parental
20 term. Then, original GO terms were plotted in a heatmap displaying their normalized
21 enrichment score (NES) and their attributed parental term as colored annotations. For the
22 analysis of inferred transcription factor activity, the vsd counts were included in an univariate

1 linear model (ulm) calculated with the decoupleR (v2.12.0) package as described
2 previously³². As transcription factor network, we used the annotated DoRothEA database for
3 human transcription factor-gene interactions from CollecTRI³³.

4
5 **Analyses of lymphocyte subsets and regulatory T cells:** Immunological analyses of the
6 preterm infant samples were performed within the first 4 days of life. Samples were taken
7 from n=28 in-phase and n=48 out-of-phase infants, always between 0800 h and 1000 h and
8 processed as previously described by our group^{34,35}. Briefly, EDTA whole blood samples were
9 stored for a maximum of 24 h at RT before processing at two different laboratories. First, the
10 central laboratory of the university hospital performed the determination of lymphocyte
11 subsets (CD8⁺/CD19⁺) using a BD FACS Canto II system (BD Bioscience, San Jose, CA, USA);
12 BD FACS Canto Clinical software using Multi test 6-Color and TBNK (T cells and B cells)
13 kits as well as Multi test CD3/CD8/CD38/HLA-DR kits according to the manufacturer's
14 instructions. Second, the flow cytometric determination of FoxP3⁺ regulatory T cells (Tregs)
15 was performed in the research laboratory of the pediatric department³⁶. Tregs were
16 determined by their position in the forward-/side-scatter plot (size/granularity) and co-
17 expression of CD3, CD4, CD25 and FoxP3. Fluorescence minus one (FMO) controls were
18 used to establish gating boundaries and to identify any background spread of
19 fluorochromes.

20

1 **Transcription factor binding prediction:** To assess whether the differences in the
2 methylation levels might have a functional relevance, we used Ciiider (Cluster Identification
3 of cis-regulatory elements). Ciiider is a bioinformatic tool designed to predict potential
4 transcription factor binding sites (TFBS) within a region of interest. It uses position weight
5 matrices (PWM) derived from curated databases, JASPAR in this case, to scan promoter or
6 intergenic regions associated with the genes of interest. It then evaluates motif
7 representation against a reference set, identifying in this way, enriched binding sites³⁷.

8
9 **Statistical analysis:** For one-to-one comparison statistical difference were assessed by
10 two-tailed T-test after confirming normality by Shapiro-Wilk test. If normality was not
11 confirmed, we used Mann-Whitney test. To assess statistical differences between three
12 groups we used one-way ANOVA followed Holm-Sidak multi comparison test, after
13 confirming normality by Shapiro-Wilk test. If normality was not confirmed, we used Kruskal-
14 Walli's test followed by Dunn's multi comparison test. GR sensitivity was assessed by two-
15 way ANOVA to assess treatment effect, group effect and the interaction effect, followed by
16 Sidak's multi comparison test. P values <0.05 were considered statistically significant. For
17 the sequencing results, the false discovery rate (FDR) adjusted p values (padj) <0.05 were
18 considered statistically significant.

19
20 **Results:**

1 With the aim to screen for global effects of aGC administration, we performed bulk RNA
2 sequencing in PBMCs from exposed preterm (aGCs, n=34) and non-exposed term infants
3 (control, n=13) and compare the transcriptome. We found that 377 genes were
4 downregulated ($p < 0.05$, $\text{Log}_2\text{Fold change} < 1$), 121 genes were upregulated ($p < 0.05$,
5 $\text{Log}_2\text{Fold change} > 1$) and 13,368 genes did not change significantly in aCG infants compared
6 to non-exposed controls (Fig 1a). Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) for gene ontology
7 (GO) terms revealed a significant change in the expression of genes related to general
8 immune and metabolic pathways, as highlighted in the volcano plot (adjusted for multiple
9 testing, $\text{padj} < 0.05$, Fig 1b). Control infants were born in term and did not receive GC,
10 therefore, there is a significant difference on birth weight and gestational age between both
11 groups (Fig S1a-c³⁰). Interestingly, the differential gene expression in the transcriptome has
12 been calculated after adjusting for birth weight and gestational age, main determinants of
13 the infants developing immune system (Fig S1a and b³⁰). Furthermore, we found that infants
14 antenatally exposed to GCs show a lower inferred GR activity (NR3C1) and a high activity for
15 NFKB1B, an inhibitory protein from the NFKB signaling pathway that is typically repressed by
16 GCs (Fig 1c). Since we have previously shown in a mouse model that the time of maternal
17 exposure to GCs determined the GR sensitivity in the offspring¹⁶, we investigated GR
18 sensitivity in the antenatally exposed infants. Estimating the maternal physiological cortisol
19 peak at 0800 h¹², we assessed samples from preterm infants exposed to GCs in the morning
20 (in-phase group) and in the evening (out-of-phase group). Six fresh blood samples per group
21 were incubated with LPS alone (100 ng/mL) or with LPS in combination with DEX at 0.01, 0.1
22 and 1 μM for 12 h at 37 °C (Fig 1d). The LPS treatment induces the production of the pro-

1 inflammatory cytokine interleukin 6 (IL-6). DEX, as agonist of the GR, suppresses the
2 production of IL-6 in a dose-dependent manner and it is used as a readout for GR sensitivity.
3 As shown in Fig 1d, samples from preterm infants whose mothers were injected out-of-
4 phase exhibited reduced GR sensitivity, as higher DEX concentrations were necessary to
5 achieve a comparable inhibition of LPS-induced IL-6 production (Fig 1d).

6 Since GCs are steroid hormones with widespread physiologic actions and GR is expressed
7 in a wide variety of cells, a reduced sensitivity of GR might have multiple functional
8 consequences. Thus, we aimed to understand how the GR differential sensitivity was
9 regulated at the molecular level and the potential functional consequences. In PBMCs, we
10 assessed the mRNA expression levels of GR and FKBP5 (the main regulator of GR sensitivity),
11 as well as methylation levels in key regulatory regions of both genes (Fig 2a)³⁸. To this aim,
12 we assessed the relative mRNA expression of *NR3C1* (gene coding for GR) or *FKBP5* between
13 groups and we did not find significant effects (Fig 2b and Fig S2b³⁰) nor in the methylation
14 levels of one of the key regulatory regions of the *NR3C1* promoter (Fig S2c and d³⁰). Thus, as
15 reported by others³⁹, the reduced GR sensitivity found in infants exposed to aGCs out-of-
16 phase cannot be explained by a differential expression of GR. However, when we analyzed
17 the methylation levels in an intronic regulatory region of *FKBP5* (Fig 2c), we found a
18 significant increase in two of the CpGs (3 and 4) in the out-of-phase group (Fig 2d and e).
19 Although, the reduced sensitivity of the GR cannot be explained by a differential expression
20 of the activity regulator FKBP5, the higher methylation levels on the regulatory region of
21 FKBP5 might have functional consequences. Therefore, we used a predictive tool (Ciiider³⁷,
22 see methods) to identify transcription factor binding sites within this region (Fig 2c).

1 Interestingly, we found that CpG3 and 4 were binding sites for transcription factors upstream
2 several immune, metabolic and proliferative signaling pathways (STAT1, 3, 4 and 5, THAP1,
3 NFATC 1 and 3 and ZNF263) and that all of them interact with GR signaling in different ways
4 (as reviewed in ⁴⁰). We reasoned that the exposure to aGCs out-of-phase might influence
5 downstream pathways differently and explain an altered sensitivity of the receptor as well as
6 its functional consequences.

7 Next, we used the transcriptome data to compare changes between preterm infants
8 exposed to aGCs out-of-phase and in-phase. We found that 233 genes were downregulated
9 ($p < 0.05$, Log2Fold change < 1), 20 genes were upregulated ($p < 0.05$, Log2Fold change > 1) and
10 13613 genes did not change significantly (Fig 3a). These two groups do not differ in birth
11 weight and gestational age (Fig S3a and b³⁰). Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) for gene
12 ontology (GO) terms revealed a significant suppression of more specific immune response
13 pathways such as antibody production and B cell signaling, leucocyte migration, cytokine
14 production, antigen presentation and cellular stress responses, as highlighted genes in the
15 volcano plot indicate (Fig 3a and b). Interestingly, we found that infants antenatally exposed
16 to GCs, showed a differential expression of transcription factors regulating cell proliferation
17 and differentiation depending on the time of day in which they were exposed (Fig 3c and d).
18 Overall, these data suggest that the exposure to aGCs at the “wrong” time of day could
19 reduce GR sensitivity, increase the methylation level on the promoter of one of the main
20 regulators of GR activity (FKBP5) where both, TF involved in immune response and GR
21 interact, leading to an unbalanced reactive state of the immune system.

1 Our observations at the molecular level, align with the lower frequency of regulatory T cells
2 (CD4⁺CD25⁺FoxP3⁺) in the out-of-phase group in the first 4 days of life, which could cause a
3 reduced immune tolerance compared to the in-phase exposed babies (Fig 4). The two groups
4 compared here did not show differences in the gestational age, birth weight, gender (Table
5 1) or the frequency of other lymphocytes such as, CD3⁺, CD8⁺, CD19⁺, NK CD16⁺/CD56⁺ (Fig
6 S4³⁰).

7 Finally, our findings suggest that antenatal exposure to synthetic GCs has an inevitable
8 effect on the infants' immune system, however, the administration of GCs in the early
9 morning, aligned with the maternal GC rhythms, might have less consequences for the
10 preterm infant than in the late evening. Our data provide strong evidence that introducing
11 this timing aspect would be advisable, whenever possible, in the clinics.

14 **Discussion:**

15 The variables that are usually considered to affect the short- and long-term outcomes of
16 aGCs treatment in a clinical setting are: drug, dose and regimen, treatment-to-delivery
17 interval and gestational and individual effects (as reviewed by⁴¹). Since GCs have a strong
18 circadian rhythm, peaking in anticipation of the active phase, we decided to focus on a less
19 explored aspect: the time of day of the maternal treatment.

20 In the present study, we first assessed the effect of aGCs administration at transcriptional
21 level in PBMCs from preterm infants and compared them with non-exposed term controls.
22 Preterm infants have immature immune systems, with reduced innate and adaptive

1 immunity because they are born too early⁴². However, the fact that we found significant
2 changes of several immune (e.g., IL1B, TNF, CXCL2, CCL3, etc) and metabolic pathways
3 (e.g., PPFIA4, ACADVL, HAL, ARSA, SLC2A, CKB, etc) even after adjusting for birth weight
4 and gestational age, suggests that aGCs exposure could be one of those early factors that
5 further compromise the preterm infants' physiology. The high activity of members of the
6 NFkB immune signaling pathway, typically repressed by GCs, suggests that a lower GR
7 activity (NR3C1) could result in multiple functional consequences for the infants exposed to
8 aGCs. GCs participate in most physiologic processes and the transcriptional responses
9 upon GR activation are cell-type specific and can vary in magnitude and directionality¹¹.
10 Therefore, the treatment with aGCs might have an inevitable effect on several aspects of
11 preterm infants' development as described by us and others^{14,16}. However, the motivation of
12 this study was to explore a way to minimize the negative consequences of this treatment.
13 Previous evidence from our laboratory showed that indeed premature infants exposed to
14 aGCs out-of-phase (i.e.: evening) were at a higher risk to develop stress coping deficits at
15 five years of age than those exposed in-phase (i.e.: morning)¹⁶. Leveraging a mouse model,
16 we explained these long-lasting changes by a basal hyperactivation of the stress axis,
17 impaired negative feedback, low expression of GR in the hypothalamus and a reduced GR
18 sensitivity in periphery¹⁶, aligned with findings from other laboratories as reviewed in⁴³. In the
19 present study, we found that GR sensitivity was reduced by the antenatal treatment with GCs
20 being lower in babies exposed out-of-phase. GR resistance has been associated to immune
21 and mood disorders and although there is no evidence of a direct link, preterm children
22 frequently suffer from both conditions (reviewed by^{17,44}).

1 Aiming to explore the molecular changes underlying the differential GR sensitivity, we first
2 assessed the mRNA expression of *NR3C1 (GR)* and *FKBP5* in PBMCs and we found no
3 difference as described by others^{16,39}. We reasoned that epigenetic changes such as
4 methylation in key regulatory regions of both genes could still explain our observation^{25,38}.
5 Interestingly, we found significantly higher levels of methylation in an intronic regulatory
6 region of the *FKBP5* gene, one of the main regulators of GR affinity to GCs and its
7 translocation to the nuclei⁴⁵ in samples from babies exposed to GCs out-of-phase. This
8 higher methylation does not significantly impact the expression of *FKBP5* itself, but it could
9 impact the way in which GCs modulate downstream pathways⁴⁶.

10 We used predictive tools to identify the TFs likely binding to the hypermethylated CpGs of
11 the *FKBP5* gene. We found that STAT1, 3, 4 and 5, NFATC, THAP1 and ZNF263 are binding in
12 that region. Interestingly, these TFs are essential for the innate and adaptive immune
13 response and for almost all of them, complex interactions with GR signaling pathways have
14 been described (recently reviewed in⁴⁰). For instance, STAT 1 and 3, NFATC and THAP1 are
15 indeed target genes of the GR⁴⁷. Reciprocally, cytokine signaling pathways including the
16 signal transducer and activator of transcription (STATs), could regulate GR affinity and its
17 translocation to the nuclei by influencing the expression of *FKBP5*^{48,49} as well as the DNA
18 binding⁵⁰. This regulatory region of *FKBP5* gene also contains binding sites for the Nuclear
19 factor of activated T-cells, cytoplasmic, calcineurin-dependent (NFATC) and THAP domain
20 containing, apoptosis associated protein (THAP1). Proteins belonging to the NFATC family of
21 transcription factors play a central role in inducible gene transcription during immune

1 response a major molecular target for the immunosuppressive drugs (reviewed in⁵¹), while
2 THAP1 has been linked to apoptosis induction⁵².

3 The reciprocal interactions between GR and immune pathways are extremely complex,
4 every immune cell expresses the receptor and it has been shown that the transcriptional
5 output could lead to both, immune suppression and immune activation depending on the
6 cell-type and context¹¹. Aiming to link the reduced GR sensitivity and the increased
7 methylation on key regulatory regions of *FKBP5*, we assessed gene expression in a broader
8 scale considering the circadian phase of GC exposure. Despite the intrinsic variability of the
9 samples, we identified differential expression of genes involved in antibody production and
10 B cell function (e.g., IGHV, IGDH, CD19), leucocyte migration and proliferation (e.g., MMP8,
11 CXCL2, C5, SRC), cytokine production (e.g., TLR10, CD40), antigen presentation (e.g., HLA,
12 LGMN, NPC2) and cellular stress responses (e.g., PRDX1, SAMD, TRIM), mainly down-
13 regulated in PBMCs from infants exposed to aGCs out-of-phase compared with those
14 exposed in-phase. Due to the nature of GC-GR signaling and the sample containing all blood
15 cells, we did not observe changes in a single pathway or cell-type specific effects. However,
16 our data provides the basis to explore more specific targets in the future using high-
17 throughput and single-cell sequencing technologies. Lastly, we compared the frequency of
18 lymphocytes between the groups and we only observed a lower frequency of regulatory T
19 cells (CD4⁺CD25⁺FoxP3⁺) in the first 4 days of life of out-of-phase infants, that may represent
20 reduced immune tolerance compared to the in-phase exposed babies.

21 The main limitation of our study is the reduced number of samples analyzed, the intrinsic
22 variability and the reduced information about the maternal conditions before and after birth.

1 Although all the samples were taken during the morning, the complexity of the study design
2 and the availability of samples did not allow us to control for the number of days between
3 the GC exposure and the infants' birth. This aspect is especially relevant because the
4 function of each immune cell is essentially circadian⁵³ and GCs are one of the main
5 entrainment signals for the circadian clock. Thus, some of the effects we see, could be
6 caused by the timing of the exogenous GCs exposure and induce mostly transient effects.
7 Further studies should assess whether the immune function could be impaired in the long-
8 term, as we already observed at the behavioral level in 5 year old infants¹⁶. Even if the effect
9 is transient, our data suggest that the exposure to aGCs at the "wrong" time of day may
10 reduce GR sensitivity and disrupt immune homeostasis and impair the capacity of the
11 newborn to cope with immune challenges during the first days/weeks of life. Aligning GC
12 administration with the maternal circadian rhythm could mitigate these effects and improve
13 immune outcomes in a population of infants who are inherently prone to immune
14 dysregulation and long-term immune impairment⁴⁴. Future clinical translation of circadian-
15 based aGCs therapies will require strong evidence ensuring that the established short-term
16 benefits, such as prevention of respiratory distress syndrome and associated morbidities
17 are preserved, while the long-term risks are reduced. This becomes particularly relevant for
18 the considerable proportion of infants who are exposed to aGCs but are delivered several
19 weeks after the treatment or even at term, therefore exposed to increased risk with little or
20 no therapeutic benefit. Our results provide a framework for evaluating this concept in larger,
21 multicenter studies.

22

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16
17 **Author contributions:**

18 I.F. contributed to design of the study, sample collection and processing as well as statistics.
19 J.H.B. prepared samples, analyzed data and prepared the figures. M.L. and N.T. prepared
20 samples and participate in data collection. H.K. and H.O. supervised the work, participate

1 in conceptualization discussion and review the manuscript. M.A. and C.H. supervised the
2 work, conceptualized the project, acquire funding and wrote the original draft of the
3 manuscript. All authors contributed in reviewing and editing the first version.
4

5 **Data availability:**

6 All the scripts used in this study for data preprocessing and analysis are available upon
7 request. Raw data is deposited in Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO XXXX). All raw data
8 included in the main Figures and the supplemental information will be shared by the
9 corresponding authors upon request.
10

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23

24 **Figure legends:**

25 **Figure 1: The GR (NR3C1) activity is reduced by the antenatal exposure to GCs. a)** RNA
26 sequencing experiment was performed from PBMCs obtained from infants antenatally
27 exposed to GCs (aGCs n=34) in comparison with non-exposed term infants (control n=13).
28 The differential gene expression is represented in a volcano plot showing that 377 genes
29 were downregulated, and 121 genes were upregulated ($p < 0.05$, $\text{Log}_2\text{Fold change} < 1$) in aGCs
30 group compared to controls. **b)** Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) identified the top gene

1 ontology (GO) terms that were activated or suppressed in aGCs infants compared to
2 controls. Genes were ranked descending based on $\log_2\text{FoldChange}^* - \log_{10}(\text{p-value})$ and
3 results were adjusted for multiple testing utilizing FDR (0.05). **c)** Analysis of inferred
4 transcription factor activity. **d)** Scheme of sample collection to assess GR sensitivity, fresh
5 blood from $n=6$ premature infants per group were incubated with lipopolysaccharide (LPS)
6 in presence of increasing concentrations of DEX. After 12 h incubation at 37°C samples were
7 centrifuged, and IL-6 measurements were run in duplicates in the supernatant. The
8 inhibition of LPS-induced IL-6 production is calculated considering LPS treatment as 100%.
9 Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM and analyzed by two-way ANOVA, treatment effect
10 $F(3,40)=21.15, p<0.0001$, group effect $F(3,40)=0.0001$ and interaction effect $F(3,40)=0.0658$.
11 Sidak's multi comparison test showed a significant difference in-phase vs out-of-phase
12 (** $p=0.0015$) for the treatment LPS+DEX $0.1 \mu\text{M}$ and a tendency ($p=0.0607$) for the treatment
13 LPS+DEX $0.01 \mu\text{M}$.

14

15 **Figure 2: Regulatory regions of FKBP5 promoter are hypermethylated in preterm infants**
16 **exposed to antenatal GCs out-of-phase. a)** Scheme of sample collection, genomic DNA
17 and RNA were isolated from PBMCs obtained from control infants (C $n=13$) and preterm
18 infants exposed to aGCs either in-phase (IP $n=17$) or out-of-phase (OP $n=17$) compared to
19 the maternal circadian rhythms. For the comparisons represented here we considered
20 samples that had both, RNA expression values and sequencing data after bisulfite
21 conversion, that is C ($n=9$), IP ($n=13$) and OP ($n=13$). **b)** Relative *FKBP5* mRNA expression was
22 assessed from the RNAseq dataset. Data is expressed as mean \pm SEM and analyzed by one-

1 way ANOVA $F(2,32)=0.7144$, $p=0.4971$. **c)** Scheme of the regulatory region of FKBP5 where
2 the methylation levels were assessed, the numbers 1 to 4 indicate the position of the 4 CpGs
3 in the sequence. Between CpG 3 and 4, predicted transcription factors binding sites are
4 indicated. **d)** Percentage of methylation in the CpGs shown in c). Data are expressed as
5 mean \pm SEM, CpG3 analyzed by one-way ANOVA $F(2,32)=11.78$, $p=0.0001$. Tukey's multi
6 comparison test: C vs OP, $***p=0.0005$ and C vs IP, $***p=0.0009$. CpG4 analyzed by Kruskal-
7 Wallis, $p=0.0592$. Dunn's multi comparison test: C vs OP, $p=0.0607$. **e)** Mean methylation
8 level in the CpGs 3 and 4. Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM and analyzed by one-way
9 ANOVA $F(2,32)=3.365$, $p=0.0472$. Tukey's multi comparison test: C vs OP, $*p=0.0390$.

10

11 **Figure 3: Multiple innate and adaptive immune response pathways are suppressed in**
12 **preterm infants exposed to antenatal GCs out-of-phase. a)** RNA sequencing experiment
13 was performed from PBMCs obtained from infants exposed to aGCs out-of-phase (OP, $n=17$)
14 in comparison with in-phase (IP, $n=17$) exposed infants. The differential gene expression is
15 represented in a volcano plot showing that 233 genes were downregulated, and 20 genes
16 were upregulated ($p<0.05$, $\text{Log}_2\text{Fold change}<1$). **b)** Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA)
17 identified the top 20 gene ontology (GO) terms that were activated or suppressed in OP
18 compared to IP. Genes were ranked descending based on $\text{log}_2\text{FoldChange}^*-\text{log}_{10}(\text{p-value})$
19 and results were adjusted for multiple testing utilizing FDR (0.05). **c)** Analysis of inferred
20 transcription factor activity for the same comparison. **d)** NR3C1 regulon, depicting genes
21 which are positively or negatively regulated by NR3C1 based on Dorothea database are

1 plotted. Most of the genes (red labelled) are aligning with regulation pattern by the univariate
2 linear model.

3
4 **Figure 4: Premature babies exposed to GCs out-of-phase show lower frequency of**
5 **regulatory T cells in the first 4 days of life.** Frequency of regulatory T cells
6 (CD4⁺CD25⁺FoxP3⁺) in the in-phase (n=28) and out-of-phase (n=48) exposed groups in the
7 first 4 days of life. Data are expressed as mean ± SEM and analyzed by two-tailed Mann-
8 Whitney test, *p=0.0184.

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1 **Table 1. Sub-cohort descriptors**

	Variable	In-phase	Out-of-phase	Controls	p value
PBMCs for RNA/DNA isolation	Cohort size	17	17	13	
	Birth weight (mean ± SD)	1447.94 ± 598.32	1638.76 ± 684.60	3577.5 ± 430.94	*p<0.0001; #p=0.2936
	Gestational age (mean ± SD)	30.60 ± 3.11	29.88 ± 3.34	39.19 ± 1.35	*p<0.0001; #p=0.6156
	Sex (% Males)	23.52	64.7	46.15	
Immune cells assessment	Cohort size	28	48	-	
	Birth weight (mean ± SD)	1226 ± 88.87	1179 ± 51.10	-	#p=0.891
	Gestational age (mean ± SD)	29.11 ± 0.56	28.89 ± 0.39	-	#p=0.738
	Sex (% Males)	42.8	43.7	-	
GR sensitivity assay	Cohort size	6	6	-	
	Birth weight (mean ± SD)	1103.33 ± 487.10	1176.66 ± 296.89	-	#p=0.484
	Gestational age (mean ± SD)	26.83 ± 3.18	29.16 ± 1.47	-	#p=0.1082
	Sex (% Males)	66.67	33.33	-	

(*) Control vs aGCs; (#) in-phase vs out-of-phase

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Figure 1
165x117 mm (x DPI)

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Figure 2
165x118 mm (x DPI)

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Figure 3
165x92 mm (x DPI)

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Figure 4
59x89 mm (x DPI)

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